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1

Given the new regime of the seas, the big challenge of the 1980s will be to achieve the economic and social objectives that developing countries have outlined for fisheries development. The major contribution of fisheries to development comes, as it has for other elements of development strategies, from its impact on indigenous groups - through the production of food, the creation of productive employment and the generation of higher income levels - in developing countries. Greater emphasis on the role of fisheries in rural development is necessary to reflect this reality.

2

Small-scale fisheries development will play a vital role in achieving those objectives.

Characteristics of Small-Scale Fisheries

3

There are millions of people around the world who are heavily dependent on water resources for both food and employment. They have long used the vast expanses of oceans, lakes and rivers, covering 70% of the earth's surface, for food production, transportation and recreation. In the developing countries some 12 million full-time fishermen, and perhaps twice that number of part-timers, are dependent on adjacent waters for a livelihood. In addition, an equal or larger number of people are employed in related activities such as fish processing, marketing

and distribution, and in boat building and net making.

4

These millions of fishermen and their families have come to consider the water as both a friend and a foe. Some operate from open beaches with boats designed for heavy surf. Others work out of somewhat protected bays. On the basis of 12 million fishermen, the average catch per man is about 6 tons per year, but we know that for many small-scale fishermen it is 1 ton or less, which is little more than they need for subsistence. Output per fisherman varies from one situation to another, reflecting the degree of labor intensity, the type of technology in export-oriented industries, and the total amount of production from waters under their natural jurisdiction or from waters of others (a situation that is changing).

5

Most small-scale fisheries are located in rural areas, in estuaries, lagoons and coastal areas in general. The enhancement of small scale fisheries **involves a decentralized form of development and participation**. Most of these millions of fishermen are located in South, and South-east Asia and Pacific countries. Nevertheless, its importance in Africa and Latin America is crucial for fisheries development.

6

These small-scale fisheries are, characteristically, small-scale, labor-intensive operations conducted by artisanal craftsmen whose level of income is low, mechanical sophistication is poor, quality of production

is low, fishing range is small, political influence is insignificant, market outlets are constrained, and employment opportunities and social mobility are restricted¹. This type of fishery contains the bulk of the 12 million full-time professional fishermen mentioned earlier, grouped in villages along the coasts of developing countries. The family-oriented form of organization, the organizational character of fishing villages, the income levels of fishing families, the different forms and the complexities in marketing and processing arrangements, and the technology used, make them unique.

7

Family and Village Organization. The participation of each fishing family member in a large array of fishery sector activities is one of the most important sociocultural characteristics of the fishery sector. The division of labor among family members varies from country to country and even within a country, but in general terms, men are mostly devoted to the catch and to the maintenance of the boats and gear, while women are mostly devoted to the processing and marketing in village areas and form the large majority of workers in the fish processing industry located in large towns. Children also perform several important activities in harvesting the resources, landing, net repairing and processing. However, usually only a few family members are fully occupied in fishing. In addition to these full-time people, there are several millions of people who supplement food supplies and/or find part-time jobs (seasonal or occasional jobs) in the fisheries. Fishing enterprises, in this respect, may overlap with other rural sector

¹ FAO, Committee on Fisheries (COFI), 1975.

activities—marine, brackish water, and freshwater aquaculture, and agriculture. The formulation of adequate organizational arrangements in small-scale fisheries development therefore requires assessment of all the rural activities to which the fishing family is devoted.

8

There are large variations in the way these activities are performed depending on the gear used in fishing. For instance, in 1955, it was estimated that in Central Vissayas, Philippines, there were several thousands of different types of gear, the most common of all being corrals, beach seines, hand lines and pots². The ownership of the fishing equipment and of the means of production determine the type of village organization. While fish resources are owned in common property and may give the impression of equalitarian access, the means of production are privately owned and its distribution is rather skew. Although the capital assets of small-scale fishing are small, the skewness of its distribution has affected its growth rate. It has been estimated that only one third of the fishermen own a boat, two thirds own some type of gear, and one third neither own a boat nor gear.

9

Marketing of fish is tied to money lending. Most marketing activities are financed by noninstitutional sources of credit which provide the necessary cash for disposing of the catch, as well as providing the cash for family needs (i.e., food, medical assistance). Typically, part of the catch is sold fresh at the village level or to adjacent towns or cities, and part of

² D. K. Emmerson, "Rethinking Artisanal Fisheries Development: Western Concepts, Asian Experiences," World Bank Staff Working Paper (Draft), January 1980.

the catch is processed (i-e., salted, dried, smoked, fermented). The participation of family members in marketing and processing depends upon the quality of infrastructure and publicly provided services (i-e., water, roads, electricity) and thus in turn on the connection between indigenous village organizations and government institutions (i-e., public works, extension services, marketing boards). Most of the time, this connection is very weak because of the geographical isolation and the small number of people living in the fishing villages.

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Income Levels. Fishing families have lower incomes than many other groups engaged in rural sector activities and certainly below most economic groups engaged in urban sector activities. This is not true for all fishermen, but it is certainly true for the large majority of those families involved in small-scale fishing. Even in Malaysia, which has one of the highest per capita incomes among the developing countries in the region, about 73% of the total number of fishermen households are living below the “poverty line”³. Their income structure varies in accordance with the ownership of the means of production and with the degree to which the family participates and controls the proceeds from marketing and processing.

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Several factors determine these low-income levels. First, since fishery resources are owned in common property, free entry to the fishery

³ T. Ch. KRiat, “Small-Scale Fisheries Development in Malaysia,” in FAO, Report of the Consultative Group Meeting on Small-Scale Fisheries Development in the South China Sea Region, No. SCS/GEN/76/9, Manila, February 1977, Appendix 2, p. 45.

sector tends to exhaust the rent from the resource, decreasing the income for each individual fisherman as the fishing effort expands. Second, the type of skills and the attitude toward fishing (i.e., cultural values) has resulted in very low labor mobility. This is particularly evident in areas where other sectors are not creating productive employment opportunities. Finally, the low level of capital expansion and the indivisible nature of existing capital (i.e., boats) limits the employment of additional family members. This last characteristic poses particular problems when the average family size of a fishing family is larger than in other groups in the economy.

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In Indonesia; for example, surveys have estimated that a fishing family has, on average, one more family member than the average family in the country. These surveys have shown that income and expenditure levels vary greatly with ownership of boats and gear. On an annual basis, the income earned by a boat owner is almost 100% higher than the income of a boatless fisherman⁴.

13

Remuneration Schemes (or distribution of proceeds) typically correspond to the existing set of formal or informal institutions (e.g., boat ownership) in the country and to the organizational arrangement prevailing in marketing and processing. In most fishing villages this is generally biased against a majority of fishermen who neither own boats nor gear. The fish caught are divided in parts where the boat owner

⁴ H. Atmowasono, "Some Notes on a Socio-Economic Study in Fisheries," in FAQ, Report of the Consultative Group Meeting on Small-Scale Fisheries Development in the South China Sea Region, No. SCS/GEN/76/9, Manila, February 1977, Appendix 2, pp» 12~17.

gets a large percentage of the catch (maybe half). The remaining part is divided equally among crew members with the participation of other villagers not directly involved in fishing. The part that the boat owner gets represents roughly one third for the boat (depreciation), one third for the engine, and one third for the owner himself. Of course these systems and the sharing schemes vary from country to country.

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Technology. The type of technology used by small-scale fisheries depends on the type of fish being caught, the physical characteristics of the continental shelf (i.e., depth, wind currents), and opportunities that fishermen have had for accumulating capital in the past. In catching fish, small-scale fisheries use a large range of gear types; this gear is used by individual fishermen (i.e., knife, bag nets) or by a group of fishermen (i.e., seine nets) with very little mechanical power as an input. Most of the technology in harvesting is labor-intensive. Although there are several fisheries that have motorized their boats, very few have mechanized the process in which the gear is supposed to operate (something that might not ever be necessary). The technology used in handling and processing is very primitive. As stated earlier, this results in significant harvesting losses. Very few small-scale fisheries use ice or have the required type of shore facilities (i.e., cold storage, ice plants).

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Marketable Surplus. Small-scale fisheries are not necessarily a synonym of subsistence fisheries. Although there are large numbers

of smallscale fisheries operating at a subsistence level, there are also significant numbers of small-scale fisheries which are commercially oriented. The degree to which a small-scale fishery becomes commercially oriented, depends on the size of the marketing surplus it is capable to generate and dispose off. There are a few small-scale fisheries that are even export oriented (i-e., Chile): several fish species and mollusks can only be harvesting using labor-intensive methods. These fish species find their consumers in either domestic or export markets⁵.

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Small-scale fisheries' marketing surplus is virtually the sole supplier of animal protein to several hundred millions of people in developing countries. For example, in Senegal, Tanzania, Ghana, The Gambia, Nigeria, Cape Verde, Sierra Leone, Togo, Indonesia, Burma, Bangladesh, India, Sri Lanka, Guyana, Trinidad, People's Democratic Republic of Yemen and Yemen Arab Republic, small-scale fisheries provide at least 75% of the total domestic demand for fish. The role in supplying animal protein to domestic markets is particularly important in isolated coastal villages in the rural areas of several other developing countries (see Table 1).

⁵ Several articles are referring to this point. See, for example, Comision Permanente del Pacifico Sur, Pacifico Sur, Seminario Regional Sobre Pesca Artesanal, Viña del Mar, Chile, October 1976.

Table 1: RELATIVE IMPORTANCE OF SMALL-SCALE FISHERIES (SSF)

Country	Production from SSF relative to total production (%)	Supply from SSF relative to domestic consumption (%)	Year
Burundi	57.7	58	1975
Cape Verde	75.3	n.a.	1976
Ghana	72.6	n.a.	1976
Nigeria	99	100	1970
Senegal	79	96.5	1975
Sierra Leone	92.5	n.a.	1976
Tanzania	100	100	1975
The Gambia	79	n.a.	1976
Togo	82.5	n.a.	1976
Bangladesh	95	n.a.	1975
Burma	83.2	100	1972
India	80	n.a.	1976
Philippines	55	55.9	1975
Sri Lanka	99.5	100	1976
Thailand	30	54.6	1970
Brazil	50	53	1975
Chile	n.a.	45	1978
Guyana	100	100	1970
Jamaica	n.a.	80	1978
Mexico	n.a.	46	1978
Trinidad	100	100	1971
Uruguay	31	62.5	1974
Venezuela	n.a.	70	1978
PDR Yemen	90	100	1975
Turkey	50	n.a.	1977
YAR	95	100	1974

Sources:

FAO Fishery Country Profile.

FAO Investment Center Preparation Reports.

FAO, Development of SSF in Southwest Asia, Column June 1977, 12A48/74/03/.

SELA. AQUARIUS. Economic System for Latin America, 1978.

Complementarities and Conflict in Development

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By contrast, large-scale fisheries are relatively capital-intensive enterprises whose level of “income are high relative to the country average, producing mostly for industrial purposes and export markets. (The definition of the terms “large” and “small” are to some extent ambiguous, since (a) the scale of operation depends on several biological (the type of fish harvested), economic and social factors; and (b) the “capital intensity” connotation of the term applies only to the subsystem of the catch, and seldom refers to the other activities carried out within the fisheries sector). There are several activities carried out by large- and small-scale fisheries that are complementary in nature. For example, (a) by developing large-scale fish eries, other forms of fisheries may have access to expanded and more concentrated local or foreign markets; (b) while small-scale fisheries create employment mostly in rural areas, large-scale fisheries create employment in urban areas; (c) while large-scale fisheries demand large and fairly sophisticated shore facilities, small-scale fisheries can make complementary use of these facilities, especially where proper design allows for this; and (d) while small-scale fisheries are solely devoted to the exploitation of resources near the coastal zones, large~scale fishing could ba. devoted to the exploitation of deep-sea fish stocks.

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However, from the development perspective of an individual country, there are many cases where the unplanned development of one or other type of fisheries results in a significant source of conflict... This arises when both enterprises compete for the same fishing grounds or for the same domestic market. While the first type of conflict is reflected through output levels, the second is reflected through price changes and profits.

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With regard to fishing grounds, conflicts result from the type of gear used and the quality of the fishing effort involved in some large-scale enterprises. For example, several types of mini-trawlers, which are mostly used for shrimp, are catching fish (i.e., by-catch) that represent, sometimes, the only source of income of the small-scale fisheries. The amount of fish caught by these trawlers can reach up to 80% of their total harvest. An example of this conflict is seen in Penang, Malaysia, where shrimp minitrawlers catch juvenile fish which breed on shrimp grounds. Consequently, it is believed that the stocks cannot be replenished, and this competition has represented a severe source of conflict.

20

Market conflicts between large and small-scale fisheries arise when large quantities of fish are supplied to limited domestic markets. Large supplies of fish will clearly decrease prices and therefore

the fishermen's income. An example of this phenomenon is in the Philippines where large as well as small-scale fisheries (so-called municipal fisheries) auction their fish in Manila only meters apart from one another. The outcome depends on the amount of fish sold and the time of the day during which the fish is sold (before or after artisanal fishermen land their product).

Development Constraints

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Many constraints in small-scale fishery development - particularly those related to consumption, marketing, credit, pricing, and organization - are similar to those affecting development in other sectors of the economy. Nevertheless, it is important to single out more of the constraints which play a special role in the development of the small-scale fishery sector. For expository purposes, these constraints have been classified as: structural, resource-based, organizational, institutional and other. Of course, all interact and form the global environment for small-scale fisheries development.

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Structural Constraints. First, one of the most important constraints to development of the fishery sector today lies in

the losses sustained before, during and after harvesting. Most harvesting losses are due to pollution of fishing waters and to the handling of the catch in the fishing boats. The greatest losses in the system, however, occur after harvesting, and it is in this stage that the losses can most effectively be minimized. The major obstacles are the lack of infrastructure and technical information and the lack of financing to provide them. Second, marketing channels are not well developed, limiting fishery sector development. In many cases, the domestic demand for fish in many developing countries is not large enough to induce additional production to compensate for productivity increases. Where these markets are developed, they allow a large proportion of the total proceeds to be absorbed by people not engaged in fishing activities. Third, the degree to which the advantages of urbanization are available to the fishermen has greatly affected small-scale fisheries development: without access to urban markets, there is little incentive for fishing villages to produce marketable surpluses of fresh fish, unless processing activities are well developed. Also, the degree of urbanization of the fishing villages correlates with the fishermen's income risks--i.e., fishermen operating far from urban centers run great risk of financial ruin from a poor catch or a poor season as their

opportunities for engaging in other incomeproducing activities are very few, or absent.

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Resource Constraints. Fourth, the special nature of the resource and its harvesting distinguishes fisheries from other sectors of the economy. Renewable resources can be sustained in perpetuity if properly managed, but there is a limit to productivity increases in the fishery sector. This limits fishermen's income growth. However, fisheries in developing countries still have considerable potential. Several traditional species occurring in the coastal waters of developing countries are underutilized. In addition, FAO estimates that production increases are possible for "other demersal" and "other pelagic" fish located in coastal areas of several developing countries (see Table 2)⁶. Also the extension of national jurisdiction up to 200 miles from the shore will potentially increase their share of existing resources, since much of the fish currently caught in coastal areas of developing countries is by foreign fleets. Not all countries have equal potential, but it is sizable, given improved management of fish resources and increased fishing effort. In addition, the formulation of a resource management policy has been

⁶ Committee on Fisheries (COFI), "Review of the State of World Fishery Resources," FAO, Rome, October 1979.

lacking: inadequate fishery sector data, resource surveys, and monitoring units that will enable early warning as to the limits and constraints of existing fishery resources under exploitation. An estimated 31 million metric tons of additional catch are within the geographical reach of developing, food-deficit countries (see Table 2, rows 6 and 7). Fifth, the configuration of the continental shelf, its plankton, narrowness and speed of coastal current impose very specific patterns on the development of the small-scale fisheries⁷. The physical characteristics of the resource and its environment will determine the appropriate technology to be used, the location of fishing activities, and the frequency within which fishing takes place.

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Institutional Constraints. Sixth, research, extension and training programs are inadequate and their inadequacy is an obstacle to small-scale fisheries development - such programs are indispensable to reaching the fishermen in order to increase productivity, minimize harvest losses, and improve resource management and resource use- In most countries there is very little research in fisheries technology, management and institution building. Extension services and training facilities

⁷ R. E. Morris, "Priorities in Development of Shelf Fisheries," in A. S. Msangi and J. J. Griffin (eds), International Conference on Marine Resource Development in Eastern Africa, The University of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania, April 1974, pp. 37-41.

Table 2: PRESENT CATCHES AND POTENTIALS FOR INCREASES FROM MAJOR GROUPS OF SPECIES

Stock	Potential (7000 t)	Total World Catch ¹				Potential Increase from Natural Stocks ('000 tons)			Aquaculture
		000 t		% of Potential		Total	Management ¹	Increased Effort	
		1966	1977	1966	1977				
Salmon	650	453	480	70	480	170	170	-	+
Flounder & Cod	6700	4692	3786	70	3786	2914	2500	400	(+)
Herring & Anchovy, etc.	15600	13709	1801	88	1801	13799	13800	-	-
Shrimp & Lobster	1670?	830	1542	50	1542	128	25	100	(+)
Tuna	2260	1031	1592	46	1592	668	100	550	(+)
Other demersal ²	37100	9628	17097	23	17097	20003	4000 ¹	16000	-
Other pelagic ²	40200	13045	28655	32	28655	11545	3000	8500	(+)
Cephalopods	(50000?)	833	1165	2	2	(50000)	-	(48000)	-
Other mollusks	Not Defined	2115	3011	-	-	-	-	Probably Large	++
Krill	(50000?)	-	123	-	0.2	(50000)	-	(50000)	-
Meso-pelagic fish	(50000?)	-	-	-	-	(50000)	-	(50000)	-
All "conventional" Total marine ³	104810	43388	53361	41	51	50120	19970	30150	
		48121	62178						

Source: FAO

¹Figures of catches exclude discards at sea. Potential increase by utilization of these discards included under "Management."

²These species are located in coastal areas of developing countries.

³Includes species groups (seaweeds, crabs, etc.) not considered in this table.

(+) Denotes aquaculture possibilities limited to fattening with specially provided food.

++ or + Denotes opportunities to increase production from aquaculture using natural food sources.

are also inadequate in many developing countries, thereby limiting the ability of artisanal fishermen of quickly adopting available technology and management information. Seventh, the management of those local government organizations dealing with small-scale fisheries is poor. Many government agencies exist only on paper, their budgets are inadequate, and the staffing insufficient to satisfy the demand for services needed by the fishery sector.

25

Eighth, credit systems and procedures have been one of the most important institutional constraints for the development of the small-scale fisheries. It is well recognized that fishery sector development requires areas a financial assistance; however, present credit systems and procedures pose severe constraints. Three major elements cause these constraints: (a) the lack of collateral; (b) the low growth rate of savings; and (c) the inadequacy of credit repayment terms. All of these problems are interrelated and have resulted in limited participation of fishermen in the existing credit system. The fishermen's inability to meet these requirements results from the difficulty

fishermen have in accumulating capital in the past and in the way (timing) this capital can be accumulated. The only source of capital accumulation is the cash proceeds from fish sales, which is related to the time spent during a fishing season which, in turn, depends on the technology used, weather conditions, and government regulations (i.e., opening and closing of the fishing season). Also, credit procedures, particularly debt repayment schedules, typically are not formulated in a way to reflect the “seasonality” of cash proceeds from fish sales. Additional elements that complicate this structure are: (a) the fact that there are many part-time fishermen, and (b) the local channels of credit are accustomed to dealing with agricultural activities and have little or no experience in dealing with small-scale fisheries. Ninth, The type of remuneration scheme has greatly affected income flows as well as income distribution. These remuneration schemes are related to the existence of complex cultural arrangements (formal or informal) that prevail at present in fishing communities; to ownership arrangements (e.g., boats and gear); and to the organization and management of production, marketing and processing activities. All of this might not be based on individual fishermen’s contribution to output. The type of remuneration systems are the major factor

determining the low rate of investment, the low quality of capital, and the low growth rate of the overall system⁸.

26

Organizational Constraints. Tenth, the fishermen's organization of their fishing activities has been a critical constraint to small-scale fisheries. Cooperatives have succeeded to varying degrees, ranging from outright failure to significant success, in such varied economic activities as production, consumption, supply, and marketing cooperatives⁹. The transformation of marketing cooperatives into production or all-purpose cooperatives has caused new problems. In production cooperatives, the cooperative organization itself - and no longer the individual fisherman - then exercises property rights over the means of production (boats and gear). This change of structure results in adequate systems for the maintenance of boats and gear, for the establishment of adequate remuneration systems. Eleventh, socioeconomic characteristics of fishing activities, including fishermen's limited needs, pose serious constraints to the development of the small-scale fishery sector. The sociological, anthropological, and cultural characteristics of fishing communities have frequently

⁸ H. Zoetewij, "Fishermen's Remuneration," in R. Turvey and J. Wiseman (eds.), *The Economics of Fisheries*, Rome, 1956, pp. 18-41.

⁹ The experience with cooperatives is mixed. The "Hokkaido" experience in Japan seems to show that cooperative organization is a necessary condition for successful fisheries development. Regardless of the degree to which cooperative type of organizations are required, there is plenty of evidence that fishermen have to get organized if credit, processing and marketing ventures are going to succeed.

not been considered as part of the overall process of designing a development strategy¹⁰; however, these characteristics have become the most serious constraint to overcome during project implementation, particularly in how they affect fishermen's participation in the decision-making process (i.e., investment, organization).

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Other Constraints. Twelfth, new ways of organizing and carrying out fishing activities (i.e., catch, marketing, processing) are necessary to achieve increases in productivity. New technology has overemphasized methods for increasing productivity of the fishing effort (i.e., catch), although it has generated the need for new services: engines demand spare parts, mechanical services, maintenance services, gasoline, etc. Given the nature (the risks involved) and seasonality of fishermen's income, the provision of those subsidiary services absorb a large proportion of the case proceeds of fishing activities. Therefore, the fishermen are impoverished as a result of new technologies and are reluctant to adopt new methods. Finally, laws, rules and regulations have also constrained the development of small-scale fisheries.

¹⁰ Several sociological and anthropological studies on fishing villages and fishery sector enterprises have been published in the last decade. Dr. R. B. Polinac's studies at the University of Rhode Island (USA) and R. Lawson of the University of Hull (England) are good examples. See also D. Emmerson for an extensive discussion on the literature. (D. K. Emmerson, "Rethinking Artisanal Fisheries Development: Western Concepts, Asian Experiences," World Bank Staff Working Paper (Draft), January 1980.)

Laws are enacted but because they do not explicitly recognize the needs of small-scale fisheries, they are not enforced, and consequently many efficiency (i.e., productivity of their fishing effort) as well as distributional (i.e., appropriation of rent for fish stocks) problems have been created for small-scale fisheries.

Development Potential and Options

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The benefits to a country from developing its small-scale fisheries are numerous. Since large numbers of people are dependent on fishing for a livelihood, small-scale fisheries are a potentially important source of increased employment and, consequently, incomes... It is frequently a means of benefiting people who are among the very poorest rural groups. Fish is also an important source of animal protein, and expansion of domestic fish supplies could improve the diet of large numbers of poor people both rural and urban. In addition, fisheries produce many valuable commodities for foreign exports, and this can generate valuable foreign exchange earnings. Given the development of EEZs, these benefits can be substantial. If pursued in an effective manner, fishery sector development could also benefit large numbers of people employed in

ancillary industries, associated with the catch, processing and marketing of fish. At the same time, small-scale fishery sector development could be an instrument for promoting a balanced regional development policy with the participation of a large number of people in the development process.

29

Development Goals. To receive such a set of benefits, developing countries should carefully outline specific goals and structure adequate development strategies. Among the primary goals, planners should consider (a) the expansion of inshore fisheries as the natural resources endowments allow - this will ensure the fullest expansion of the traditional artisanal fishing through either increasing fishing activities or increase production of existing boats, depending on the local situation; (b) the provision of adequate infrastructure facilities which would include ports and landing piers, ice plants and cold storage, transport systems, marketing centers and distribution networks; (c) the improvement of marketing chains since, in many developing countries, markets have not been large enough to justify the intensification of the existing fishing effort, or to compensate productivity increases in production and processing; (d) the minimization of harvesting

losses, using ice in boats, constructing adequate shore facilities, improving processing at the village level, and providing adequate transport; (e) the improvement of fishery sector administration, including government extension and training systems, availability of credit and adoption of new technology; and (f) the enhancement of fishermen organization schemes.

30

The options open to a nation in developing its fisheries are determined, inter alia, by the available resources, market conditions, the objectives of development, the technology used and available, and the structure of the fishing industry. As each of these factors varies from one situation to another, so does the potential for development and the range of options available. Although the scope for large-scale expansions of fisheries appears relatively limited, provided that a feasible opportunity can be found, the potential for expansion of small-scale, indigenous fisheries in many developing countries is quite favorable. In general, some of the resource base characteristics that must be taken into account include: (i) the availability of fish stocks; (ii) the equipment and skills of fishermen, processors and others; (iii) the competition with other sectors for resources; (iv)

the interaction - relative shares of catch and markets - between small and large-scale fisheries; (v) the changing resource boundaries, especially associated with the ZEZ; and (vi) available infrastructure, both physical and administrative, to permit such development.

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Technological Path. In formulating options for the development of fisheries, an assessment must be made of the existing and potential options available within the technological path available to individual countries. This technological path - from a very labor-intensive, indigenous fishery to a very capital-intensive fishery - is defined by several economic, social, and cultural characteristics of fishery sector enterprises. Fishery sector projects will, in general, produce changes of one or more of those characteristics in fishery enterprises and, consequently, move them to different stages along such a technological path. The definition of fishery sector development options is, in fact, a process where decision makers choose (or assess the consequences of choosing) one or more points along this technological path over time. The moves along these technological paths would be evaluated in light of country objectives, constrained by economic, biological,

social, and cultural factors.

32

The time that it takes to move along the technological path is a very important element for consideration. If one suggests, in a narrow sense, that moves from small- to large-scale fisheries reflect moves along this technological path, it is important to recall that most European economies have experienced such a transition; this transition has taken them several decades and has been delineated by several generations. The rate at which this transition will take place in developing countries is unknown, although evidence suggests that several countries are planning to move rapidly in exploiting the opportunities they meet along the technological path. This in no case means that the small-scale, indigenous fisheries will disappear.¹¹

33

Which form of existing fisheries in developing countries can move along the technological path is another important element for consideration. For the small-scale fisheries this matter has

¹¹ Despite the continuous development of deep-sea fisheries. (coastal as well as long-distance fishing) in developed countries, small-scale fisheries are still an important part of the fishery sector structure and organization. Excellent examples could be found in Japan, Norway, and Canada where small-scale coastal fisheries are one of the principal forms of fisheries. This coexistence of large- and small-scale fisheries - or the survival of small-scale fisheries industry - is due to the nature and physical structure of the continental shelf, the type of fish or shellfish varieties under production, the quality of fish to be supplied to domestic (or export) markets, and the like. It is worth mentioning that, given today's prices on energy inputs (oil products), it becomes an important factor in estimating small-scale fisheries development.

particular significance. Policy makers will have to assess (a) if it is possible to move small-scale fisheries with minimal disruption of institutional arrangements and fishermen's income; and (b) if it is possible (or necessary) to move small-scale fisheries while still maximizing the welfare of millions of fishing families, or is technology available to increase the productivity of artisanal fishermen's fishing effort, maintaining an acceptable degree of labor intensity. The challenge for the 1980s is, in sum, to define and provide the required ingredients for developing the small-scale fisheries, *pari passu*, with substantial increases in employment, food production, regional income, and development in general.

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Fisheries Development Typology. For expository purposes, one would have to identify the elements which define a typology of fishery sectors in developing countries. This typology, which is to a large extent unique to each individual country, will serve us to clearly formulate adequate development strategies. Elements for a typology across individual fishery enterprises is also an important part for the design and formulation of fishery sector projects and deserve mention here. This paper discusses three

important elements of typology: (a) resource endowments, (b) population density and urbanization rate, and (c). extent of nonfishing activities at the village level.

35

Different combinations of these elements produce different types of developmental environments within which fishery investment might occur on a global basis and to which policy principles may apply. For example, in some areas of the world, fishing resource endowments are not sufficient to cope with the level of fishing effort applied--these are fish deficient areas. Most of these areas are characterized by a total and sustained decrease in catch (on a fisherman. basis) and by a catch of fish of lower quality (small size). Lack of resource management planning, nonenforceable licensing systems (for boat and gear) and, in many cases, pollution have resulted in total losses for the fishing communities. In areas where the resources have not reached the critical zone (i.e., they are still renewable), strict control of fishing may help to restore the resource. In areas where fishing resources have passed their critical zone and depletion is imminent, restocking, when possible, is necessary, and/or resettlement of fishermen must take place. In areas

where there is an abundance of fish, distinction should be made between nontraditional and traditional species. In these fish-abundant areas, increases in the fishing effort, accompanied by a balanced project package (i.e., landing, processing, marketing) may produce large profits to fishermen. Resource endowment, therefore, will greatly affect the fishery development strategy in any particular area.

36

The settlement pattern and rate of urbanization also influence the development of a fishery. The degree of remoteness of a fishing village from shore facilities required, and the appropriate processing and marketing infrastructure are important constraints. When large urban centers are difficult to reach and transportation is primitive, processing at village level (labor intensive) must be developed (e.g., cured fish). There is a need for processing-oriented enterprises. On the other hand, in villages which are undergoing rapid urbanization (and thus face an increasing demand for fish) or are close to rapidly growing urban centers, the necessity of processing at village level may diminish. The closer the village is to a large urban center, the more important marketing activities become. In such situations

there is a need for market-oriented enterprises.

37

The existing production base at the village level is an important factor in that it defines the extent to which time can be apportioned between fishing and nonfishing activities, particularly agriculture or aquaculture (e.g., brackish water fish culture). In some areas, people devote time exclusively to fishing, and the production base of the village is so poor that fishing is the only source of income; these are full-time fishing areas. In other areas, where the production base is rich or allows aquaculture or other employment-generating activity to develop, fishing income is augmented from these nonfishing activities; these are part-time fishing areas. (Seasonality of fishing activities may also be important here.)

Elements of Strategy

38

Project Formulation. Fisheries development strategies should favor integrated programs by balancing the systems of catch, handling, processing, marketing and distribution. There is a need to design projects that will increase production only in

resource-abundant areas or areas where, under an explicit set of resource management policies, the development stages of other subsystems will lead to a maximum social return to the economy. Resource assessment, improvement in research, extension and training will be indispensable activities in fulfilling the aforementioned strategy.

39

In resource-abundant areas, where no overexploitation of resources is taking place, one would consider the formulation of projects with a high degree of vertical integration--to integrate small-scale fisheries" catch with handling, processing, marketing and distribution. However, in areas where overexploitation of resources is taking place and, therefore, an additional increase in productivity of existing fishing effort is not socially optimal, one would consider the formulation of projects with a high degree of horizontal integration--to integrate small-scale fisheries with marine and freshwater aquaculture or even agriculture. This strategy will keep the pressure off existing resources by allowing fishermen to exploit marine, brackish, or freshwater aquaculture, or to exploit agricultural products. This horizontal integration will not only increase the future productivity of heavily

exploited resources but also will stabilize fishermen's incomes. Other strategies can be implemented through the formulation of projects with a mix of the aforementioned strategies.

40

Moreover, the strategies would be incomplete if resource management were not considered a key element in fisheries development. Most fishery sector projects are designed to increase the productivity of fishing, which will pay off only if fishery resources are well managed. This element of the strategy would include proper systems for the identification and preparation of adequate investment projects as well as covering all the regulatory aspects - licensing, laws and regulations, control of fishing gear - at both the national and the individual fishery-enterprise levels.

41

In addition, preference must be given to projects with high socioeconomic impact. The strategy should be formulated in such a way as to help meet the food and nutrition needs of the population, to provide income and employment opportunities for small-scale fishermen, and to advance rural development.

In the past, relatively little integration of fisheries and rural development has taken place. In capture fisheries, projects may be designed to maximize the socioeconomic benefits to fishing families, for example, by promoting local boat building, net making or repairing, and labor-intensive fish processing within the village. This integration will take place if those organizations relevant to fishing and related activities are improved.

42

Furthermore, current emphasis on the achievement of equity in economic development, along with world food problems, has brought about a renewed interest in the use of fish as a source of protein for rural and urban populations. However, the equity issue is frequently overlooked in the preparation of fishery sector projects. It requires a focus on the rural producers as well as on both the rural and urban consumers. Likewise, the strategies should also consider the design of projects as modules to be expanded additively. At the initial stages of development, planners ought to consider projects that are replicable. This replicability is in terms of the diversity of institutions to be used and in terms of the appropriate technology selected to maximize employment and lift existing marketing constraints.

Fishery development programs should therefore seek to build technology and production improvements into existing structure rather than impose packages of entirely alien innovations.

43

Finally, in both the design and justification of national fishery sector programs, there is a need to give explicit attention to environmental concerns: resource conservation and the interrelationship of the effects of fisheries projects with each other and with other sectors of the economy (e.g., pollution from industrial projects, misallocation of water use in irrigation projects). Environmental programs should include the stocking of fish in rivers and lakes, improvement in present resource management techniques, and the provision of surveillance systems to prevent over-exploitation. Given the “common property” nature of the resources, project design must consider the context of other projects financed in the region; a regional approach to project design and formulation would be desirable in many instances (i.e., West Africa).

44

Fishery Sector Management. The maximum effectiveness

in implementing fishery sector development strategies will be achieved not only as a result of project formulation and design - development “with” investment - but also as a result of adequate sector management policies--development “without” investment. Sector management involves particularly the regulation, control and implementation of fishing activities within the EEZs, especially those activities related to the assessment and conservation (i.e., optimal use rates over time) of existing fish stocks.

45

Besides those controls which are available to all economic sectors (ie., taxes, subsidies), the fishery sector is unique because of the common property nature of its resources. Fishery sector management needs an additional set of regulations--those that limit access to the resources. Most often, this access is achieved by controlling the quantity of fish or the size of the fish caught, using different methods for licensing, quotas, seasonal closures, closed fishing areas and regulation of fishing gear. These policies will affect the sector allocation of resources and the distribution of rent among participants.

46

The implementation of resource management programs is difficult because conflicts of interest arise - between producers and consumers, between large and small-scale fisheries, between the fishery sector and other sectors of the economy (i.e., pollution, oil exploitation), and between domestic and foreign fleets. The conflict between domestic and foreign interests is compounded by the fact that several foreign fleets used to have free access to the developing countries' coastal resources. Rational resource management programs may help to resolve such conflicts¹².

Directions for the Future

47

Small-scale fisheries--in various forms--can contribute to both a fuller and more economical utilization of existing resources and to the increased productivity of a population which has fishing as its only or main source of income and welfare; therefore, the economic and social development of small-scale fisheries has become a major concern of many developing countries. This reflects a marked change in that, until recently, much of

¹² Two of the resource management instruments in current use are joint ventures and production quotas. Several FAO publications refer to the advantages and disadvantages of different resource management policies.

the development effort in world fisheries has Focused on large-scale, relatively capital-intensive fishery activities, frequently linked to processing and marketing. The major objective has been to increase production at high returns to investment.

48

Consequently, the basic goal of World Bank fishery sector policy is to improve the welfare of low-income fishermen by increasing their productivity, and to meet the needs of low-income consumers by supplying larger amounts of a relatively cheap source of protein to domestic markets, both in rural and urban areas. To accomplish this set of objectives, the World Bank is placing major emphasis on the development of small-scale fisheries. In particular, there is greater emphasis on marketing, processing and distribution, and a concerted effort toward providing an environment for decentralized development with active participation by those who need to get involved.

49

Fisheries development in most countries will be influenced by the present and potential demand for fish, available technology and cost of production. The rising prices of petroleum products

and timber and the high cost of boat building will make fishing vessels increasingly costly to operate. Developing countries will have to give significant priority to the adoption of development strategies which take account of the steady increase in energy cost. In this respect, they have an advantage because their nearness to the fishing grounds makes it possible to use smaller and less expensive boats.

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In light of these considerations, the Bank is planning to support fishery sector policies which will: (a) de-emphasize, and where appropriate reverse, the overexploitation of stocks by being extremely selective - through investment as well as resource management; (b) reformulate those projects solely devoted to increase the catch, to include other dimensions of fishing development; (d). seek to minimize losses in fish catching, handling, processing and marketing; (e) favor changes in trade patterns toward increasing fish availability in domestic markets; (f) maximize the impacts of investment activities on people's welfare; and (g) lead to better management of total fishing resources for the national benefit. To do this, Bank policy should remain flexible and capable of further adaptation. While

approaches in some areas, are still experimental, enough has already been learned from experience to draw conclusions for the future.

51

In developing an individual fishery, a balance should be ascertained between the various stages of activities such as catching, processing and marketing. Fisheries projects will only be developed in those areas where adequate fish resources are available to ensure the productivity of the fishing effort proposed and still sustain production over time. Projects may include the introduction of boats and gear and processing equipment, but improving the management of fish stocks will also have components designed to increase output through and, not the least, by improving infrastructure such as roads and landing facilities. Fishery sector projects should emphasize the role of resource management, and to this end may provide funds for stock assessment surveys and, where feasible, the restocking of, say, lakes, and rivers. The environmental impact which projects may have in other sectors of the economy (i-e., agriculture, industry) and which may in turn affect the performance of fisheries projects, e.g., marine and inland aquaculture, will also

be carefully considered.

52

The Bank will endeavor to assist in minimizing losses by introducing appropriate sanitation and technologies for the handling of fish on the boat, during landing, in processing at the village level and in the subsequent marketing and distribution. Small-scale fisheries projects will help to finance both the required physical investment in refrigeration and other processing plants as well as infrastructure such as water supply and landing facilities. Institutional development to cope with the major constraints due to lack of adequate systems for research, training, education and extension service will also be supported.

53

Finally, when considering the development of a fishery, the Bank is helping developing countries establish sound marketing and distribution systems to reach rural and urban consumers and, where relevant, develop exports of fish and fishing products. In urban centers, fishery sector projects are including the construction or rehabilitation of market yards and the expansion of fish distribution systems (i-e., transport, wholesale ports) to

reach large numbers of low-income neighborhoods. The Bank is also assisting in the financing of infrastructure and in providing technical assistance to formulate adequate marketing and nutrition studies.

54

Environmental Considerations. Though many developing countries have not, in the past, given high priority to ecological considerations, awareness of the ecological consequences of development is growing rapidly. The Bank assists in promoting this awareness by informing clients of specific social benefits and costs from particular projects or development strategies and their potential effects on the environment. In countries where there are no adequate natural resource conservation programs or institutions, the Bank is supporting their development. At all times, it will satisfy itself that projects or programs will not result in overexploitation of fish stocks.

55

The Bank may also support inventories of fishery resources in member countries. These should include not only inventories of indigenous aquatic species but also assessments of the

potential for introducing new varieties into a region's rivers, lakes and reservoirs, and surveys of the extent to which lagoons, estuaries, brackish water systems and low-quality land might be utilized.

56

The Bank also exercises care in supporting irrigation projects. and project use of pesticides, where very high net social losses to fisheries may result. The net social losses to fisheries will be considered in calculating the net social returns to irrigation projects. In addition, evaluations of the perceivable effects of irrigation or industrial projects on the fisheries environment will be considered at appraisal of those projects.

57

Research. Through its project activities, the Bank has already given support to fishery research programs in a number of countries. In the future, research components should expand to include learning more about the motivation of people in rural areas; analyzing the major effects of fisheries projects on rural communities; formulating an efficient monitoring system and identifying those features of successful projects which can

be replicated in other projects; acquiring more information about the resources (fish, land, water) available to rural people; financing resource inventory projects to monitor national income production and employment impacts of projects at the regional and local levels; adapting new technologies to national and local conditions; and determining fish consumption patterns and demands by low income consumers.

58

The Bank is prepared to support the establishment of an international program to carry out applied research in small-scale fisheries technology, biology, sociology, economics and anthropology. This may take the form of an international network for research and technology transfers or a specialized institution. Where appropriate, the Bank is also prepared to support pilot projects to test newly developed approaches, allow for universal integration of fishing activities, focus on specific problems and gather baseline data for the determination of required fishing effort.

59

Training. Among the main constraints faced when expanding

smaller large-scale fisheries are the shortage of indigenous supervisory and managerial staff and the lack of training of fishermen and other family members. Many developing countries are requesting assistance for the establishment of fisheries training programs. Small-scale fisheries projects will include training components to meet the needs of persons involved in all fishing activities (i.e., catch, handling, marketing, processing, distribution). The training process must consider “on the job” training, supplemented with more formal training when necessary. Those projects will avoid the creation and the establishment of permanent training institutions devoted to upgrade and promote university-level graduates. The training should particularly emphasize better methods of handling and post-harvesting technology: to help in eliminating existing postharvest losses. Training of people associated with shipyards and mechanical services - preferably from the fishing villages - will be another important component in small-scale fishery projects.

60

Fishing training may also include the formulation of pilot operations where full participation of fishermen must be

encouraged. The use of experimental vessels, new type of engines, new fishing methods, and new harvesting and processing technologies should be considered an integral part of the training. This training must also include those areas dealing with the Management of fisheries resources, formation of local organizations and all those subjects which would enhance the performance of fishery sector projects.

61

Technology. Current technical know-how in small-scale fisheries seem to be far ahead of the actual applications in most developing countries. The major emphasis in World Bank financed projects is on the transfer and application of already existing technology. The appropriateness of technological packages in fisheries projects have to be assessed within the cultural, institutional and socioeconomic framework of the project area. However, it is important to note that the Bank appraises these packages very carefully during preparation and appraisal; particularly with regard to the scale of the operation (changes in the capital / labor ratios), to the optimization of existing resources (i.e., fish stocks, labor), to the complexities in repairing and maintaining the proposed equipment and in its transport, and to the induced

demand for cash proceeds involved.

62

Institutions. The weakness, or lack, of fishery institutions, including extension programs, training programs, local fishermen's organizations and sector management machinery, has proved perhaps the single most important obstacle to increasing fishery activity. Fresh approaches to institutional arrangements are needed if small-scale fisheries are to be developed. Support to fishery sector institutions will therefore be directed toward local organizations that manage village-oriented fisheries activities. Close cooperation will be encouraged between agencies dealing with rural fish farming and agencies engaged in other phases of the rural development process. Elements of institutional strengthening suitable for financial support include sector review of the needs for manpower training and technical assistance; technical assistance to fishery services and fishery development authorities; missions to assist governments in the preparation or revision of fisheries policies (e.g., laws, regulations, licensing, pricing, land use plans); financing the establishment of credit, education, training and research facilities.

63

Fishery Sector Planning. The Bank is helping governments to formulate fishery sector development strategies, with special emphasis on rural and environmental fishery sector issues. The Bank will continue to cooperate with other multilateral and bilateral agencies that have specialized knowledge, in particular the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) through the Cooperative Program.

64

Deployment of Resources. World Bank resources, though relatively small at present, have been allocated in part to the development of small-scale fisheries. This is particularly evident during the last 5 years (1975-1980) where a significant % of total funds have benefited artisanal fisheries. In the future, the Bank expects to devote a substantially larger amount of funds to enhance rural development through small-scale fisheries development.

65

The experience and constraints faced by some of the Bank projects have provided part of the material already present in the

previous paragraphs. Most of these projects include components dealing with an increased productivity of existing fishing effort (i.e., increase the quantum of production); provide shore facilities like landing facilities, cold storage and ice plants (i.e., increase the quality of production); improve existing marketing and distribution systems (i.e., reach the largest number of rural as well as urban consumers); and create the necessary environment for the transfer of appropriate technology and institution building - the planning and management of existing fishery sector natural resources.

-----Dr. Alfredo Sfeir-Younis
Dzambling Cho Tab Khen
World Bank, 1980-----